

AN INNOVATIVE LABORATORY STAND FOR SELF-REGULATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE PROSPECTS OF SOLAR COLLECTORS

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ABSTRACT: *In particular, attention is paid to protecting solar collectors from heat loss in winter, freezing in the absence of sunlight during a sharp cold snap of the day. The development of innovative technologies for the use of solar energy in the country, increasing its efficiency, as well as the development of scientific research in this area, including the formation of skills and a broad understanding of the use of solar energy, a laboratory bench was provided for monitoring internal processes in information systems. Current use of these methods has seen electrical heating of solar collectors, the use of antifreeze, the use of slow circulation, drainage and high energy costs. The main energy saving is provided by protecting solar collectors from damage due to the fact that in winter and summer periods, the self-drainage is completely drained by an automated system when the circulation pump stops. In particular, the analysis of solar collectors in foreign experience, the content and essence of expanding the prospects for use in our solar country is presented, scientific proposals and practical recommendations for improving the industry are presented.*

KEYWORDS: *Development Solar collectors, self-draining energy-saving device, high power, heat carrier heating water.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The use of renewable energy sources, ie solar energy, is highly effective in our country. The sunny region of Uzbekistan has about 300-330 days of sunshine. In a solar collector, the most effective way to prevent the sudden change of climate, i.e. the exchange of air with the heat carrier during the winter season, especially in the evening, is to freeze and degrade, a method of self-drainage. One of the most beneficial areas in the use of solar energy is the solar heating and hot water supply systems of these buildings.

The volume of commissioning of solar collectors has been declining since 2009. From this point on, the search for ways to reduce the cost of solar collectors and the existing price in the system as a whole In this situation, which has become one of the main tasks of European solar science, to simplify them in order to identify and assess key reserves for improving the efficiency of solar energy , increasing their reliability and lowering their cost is emerging as one of the most pressing issues at the moment[1].

Solar heat supply systems differ from traditional systems in that they have solar collectors, solar collectors are distinguished by their extreme sensitivity to the temperature regime of operation of systems than fuel or electric generators of heat.

If the final temperature of the heated water due to the high (above 1000°C) temperature caused by the combustion of fuel in fuel-fired generators has practically no effect on their efficiency, then increasing the operating temperature of the water heater by one degree in the first approach for solar water heaters leads to a decrease in the coefficient by 1-2%. Therefore, in the process of generating heat energy in solar collectors, its accumulation in the heat accumulator, transmission to the consumer and loss of temperature potential when working with a duplication source serve as the main criteria for evaluating the efficiency of solar water heating installations.

II. RESEARCH OF METHOD.

Innovative energy-saving laboratory stand for seasonal testing of solar collectors in different conditions has been created to develop innovative technologies in the field of solar energy, increase its efficiency, as well as develop skills in the use of university students and schoolchildren in this field and gain a broad understanding of solar energy.

In the first place of the laboratory stand was prepared a general drawing project. The device of the solar collector was created based on the principle of the brain, to monitor the movement of the heat carrier and internal processes, which is adapted to the location of ultrasonic special sensors that control the speed of movement of the heat carrier, its pressure and temperature at the inlet and outlet. At the top, a 50-liter heat-storage accumulator tank was installed for a simple insulated self-flowing system to prevent heat loss[2].

Fig.1. Seasonal testing of solar collectors under different conditions is the process of obtaining results in the summer of an innovative energy-saving laboratory stand.

Protection of the solar collector from damage to increase the efficiency and efficiency of energy-saving and reliable self-drainage when the system is in active state, ie the location of air when the circulating pump is running and the location of air when the pump stops. By means of a hydraulic device, the extinguishing of hydraulic shocks that occur during system operation accelerates heat exchange and has a number of benefits. There is a device that shows the consumption of the heat carrier. All control and control board parts were installed[3].

When the solar collector is connected to a simple system and other auxiliary devices, mainly to the two-circuit boiler currently widely used, the performance was tested on a hybrid basis and an effective result was obtained. The created innovative energy-saving laboratory stand allows you to adjust the slope of the solar collector from horizontal to vertical. Due to the instability of the sun, the operation of the solar collector based on the lighting lamp in the cloudy and evening part of the day is provided, and it has its own special program and works in an automated mode.

Seasonal testing of the created solar collectors in different conditions allows to get acquainted with different options of rotation of the innovative energy-saving laboratory stand heat carrier: by means of a thermosyphon and a pump[4]. The structural assembly of the device is made of space-welded square tubes covered with light gray paint with shagreen texture. placed.

III. RESULTS AND EXPERIMENTAL INFORMATION

Solar collectors are a key element of aquatic solar heat supply systems and operate in conditions of extremely variable sources of solar energy and outdoor air temperature in a very wide range: from low negative values in winter to high positive values in summer. Such conditions of use can cause failure of solar collectors: in winter as a result of freezing of water at night, and in summer - during the day in the mode of stagnation (boiling stops) and the temperature inside solar collectors rises to 200°S in flat collectors and 300°C in vacuum. as a result.

The use of antifreeze in high-capacity solar installations is a very expensive solution due to the large area of solar collectors, moreover, this solution does not solve the problem of summer protection of solar collectors due to antifreeze boiling in summer. In self-draining solar systems, solar collectors are protected from damage due to the fact that there is complete drainage when the circulation pump stops in both winter and summer seasons. However, certain solutions of self-draining solar devices, which are widely used in world practice, include excessive consumption of electricity to circulate the heat carrier, hydraulic shocks when circulating pumps stop, low reliability and large temperature potential losses in intermediate heat exchangers.

IV. CONCLUSION

Slightly draining helium facilities were carried out with research plans close to the priorities and state programs of scientific research in the country. These low-drainage solar facilities are in line with the priority development of science and technology of the Republic "Development of renewable energy sources." There are 4 main ways to protect solar collectors from damage: draining, using antifreeze, working with electricity, analyzing for slow circulation, superiority, and welcoming people who want to keep workers at home.

Self-draining solar devices are relatively energy-efficient and reliable self-draining solar devices with a simple single-circuit high-power solar system that reduces electricity consumption by 60%, eliminates hydraulic shocks when circulating pumps stop, and increases thermal efficiency by up to 20%. focused on output and implementation.

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